

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 9th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held at in Dean chamber of College of Physiotherapy, Pandeshwar on 22.2.2021.

Members present were:-

Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson)

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member)

Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member)

Dr. N. Mageswaran (Member)

Dr. Pathak Anupama (Member)

Members not present were:

Dr. Bhargav Dave (External member)

Dr. K. Vijay Kumar (External member)

At the onset the Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar welcomed the members and placed the agenda for the deliberations of the members. The following deliberations were made as per the circulated agenda:

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 8.12.2020

- The minutes of the BOS meeting held on 8th December 2020 were circulated among the BOS members. Since no comment has been received, this BOS has approved the minutes of the BOS meeting.

**2. Revision of Master of Physiotherapy (MPT) regulations under point number 19-
Dissertation:**

-The university internal marks for dissertation in each semester in the old regulations was 10 marks. But since it holds more weightage it was proposed by Dr. Thrishala Noronha and seconded by Dr. S. Rajasekar to increase the internal marks to 50. Also the final semester university examination marks in Dissertation viva-voce to be changed to 50 instead of 60 to give equal weightage to internal and external marks. These regulations will be implemented for MPT 2019 batch onwards.

REGISTRAR
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-Resolution: The members discussed on this matter and unanimously resolved to recommend the changes to the Academic council for further approval.

3. To revise credits of certain courses of all semesters of MPT across all electives:

-Since course credits for the clinical training was not clearly stated, it was proposed by Dr. N. Mageswaran and seconded by Dr. Thrishala Noronha that the credits under certain courses of MPT programme be revised by adding additional credit for clinical training across all the electives. This will be implemented from the batch of 2019 onwards.

1) Semester I- Credits revised for courses-

Kinesiology and Pathomechanics (19MPT102)

Ethics and Evidence Based Practice (19MPT103)

2) Semester II- Credits revised for courses-

Differential Diagnosis for Physiotherapists (19MPT203)

Electrophysiology and Functional Diagnosis Practical (19MPT205)

3) Semester III- Credits revised for courses-

Physiotherapeutics-I Practical (19MPT3G2)

Elective courses Assessment and Management-I Practical (19MPT313-19MPT363)

4) Semester IV- Credits revised for courses-

Physiotherapeutics-II Practical (19MPT4G2)

Elective courses Assessment and Management-II Practical (19MPT413-19MPT463)

-Resolution: The members discussed and resolved to recommend the changes to the Academic council for further approval.

4. Addition of Dissertation as a course in each semester of MPT across all electives

-Dissertation work in each semester carries 2 credits. However, it was not added as a course. This would interfere with the calculation of SGPA for it. Hence it was proposed by Dr. Thrishala Noronha and seconded by Dr. Anupama Pathak that Dissertation work must be added as a course in each semester for all the electives. This will be implemented from the batch of 2019 onwards.

Semester I course will be titled as **Dissertation-I**

Semester II course will be titled as **Dissertation-II**

Semester III course will be titled as **Dissertation-III**

Semester IV course will be titled as **Dissertation-IV**

5. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

-The Chairperson requested the Board members to prepare the panel of examiners for 1st semester end examination of BPT and MPT programme.

-Resolution: The Board members prepared the panel of examiners for the 1st semester end examination of BPT and MPT, and resolved to recommend the same to the University and send the panel of examiners list in a sealed cover to Registrar (Evaluation).

6. Introduction of Value added courses for BPT and MPT for the year 2021-22.

Chairperson explained the requirement for adding value added course (not a part of curriculum) for BPT and MPT programmes.

-Resolution: The board discussed on this matter and it was decided that,

- for BPT 1st year- Introduction to computers; BPT 2nd year- Diet and Nutrition; BPT 3rd year and 4th year- Hospital Administration
- for MPT 1st year- Advanced cardiac life support (ACLS); MPT 2nd year- Robotics in Physiotherapy

The meeting started at 10.00am and ended at 12.00pm with thanks to the Chair.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 10th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held in Dean's chamber of College of Physiotherapy, City campus, Pandeshwar on 15.11.2021.

The following members were present:

Dr. Rajasekar S	-	Chairperson	
Dr. Ajay Kumar	-	Member	
Dr. Thrishala Noronha	-	Member	
Dr. N. Mageswaran	-	Member	
Dr. Pathak Anupama	-	Member	

Leave of absence:

Leave of absence was granted to
Dr. Bhargav Dave (External member) and
Dr. K. Vijay Kumar (External member) by the Chairperson, Board of Studies.

The Chairman welcomed all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting was thereafter deliberated by Dr. Thrishala Noronha on agenda items as had been approved by the Chairperson.

AGENDA

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 22.02.2021.
2. To consider and approve the Curriculum and syllabus for BPT according to NEP 2020.
3. To consider and approve the revised curriculum and syllabus for MPT 2021 batch.
4. Planning the academic calendar for BPT and MPT for the academic year 2021-22.
5. Formation of Board of Examiners (BOE) for BPT and MPT program examination for 2021-22.
6. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 22.02.2021.

- The minutes of the BOS meeting held on 22nd February 2021 was circulated among the BOS members. Since no comment has been received, this BOS has approved the minutes of the meeting.

2. To consider and approve the Curriculum and syllabus for BPT according to NEP 2020.

-The Chairperson informed the house that the based on the feedback received from the stakeholders regarding the curriculum, changes have been made and syllabus for BPT for the batch of 2021 has been structured according to NEP 2020 and is ready for approval.

-Resolution: The members considered the curriculum and syllabus for BPT and discussed different issues. Finally, it was approved and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval. It was also decided that the course can be introduced under College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University from 2021 batch onwards. The structuring and changes made are as follows:

Sl. No	Course Code	Course Name	Modification
1.	21BPTDSC01	Psychology and Sociology	Both psychology and sociology which were separate courses earlier are now merged and made into one.
2.	21BPTDSC02	Human Anatomy-I	Human Anatomy-I Theory and Practical course units are merged and made as one course.
3.	21BPTDSC03	Human Physiology-I	Human Physiology-I Theory and Practical course units are merged and made as one course. Also, practical syllabus has been fine-tuned with introduction of new practical components based on the skill requirements.
4.	21BPTAECC02(NK)	Kannada-I for non-Kannadigas	New course introduced as per NEP.
5.	21BPTAECC02(K)	Kannada-I for Kannadigas	New course introduced as per NEP.
6.	21BPTSEC01	Introduction to basic skills in patient care-I	Converted from non-credit to credit course carrying 2 credits.
7.	21BPTSEC02	NSS/Cultural/sports	Value based course added as per NEP.
8.	21BPTDSC04	Human Anatomy-II	Human Anatomy-II Theory and Practical course units are merged and made as one course.
9.	21BPTDSC05	Human Physiology-II	Human Physiology-II Theory and Practical course units are merged and made as one course.
10.	21BPTAECC02(NK)	Kannada-II for non-Kannadigas	New course introduced as per NEP.
11.	21BPTAECC02(K)	Kannada-II for Kannadigas	New course introduced as per NEP.
12.	21BPTSEC03	Basic Nursing and First Aid	Earlier a non-credit course has been now introduced as credit based course carrying 2 credits.
13.	21BPTSEC04	Introduction to basic skills in patient care-II	Converted from non-credit to credit course carrying 2 credits.

14.	21BPTDSC07	Pathology and Microbiology	Both psychology and sociology which were separate courses earlier are now merged and made into one.
15.	21BPTDSC08	Exercise Therapy-I	Theory and Practical course modules are merged and made as one course.
16.	21BPTDSC09	Biomechanics and Kinesiology-I	Theory and Practical course modules are merged and made as one course.
17.	21BPTAECC06	French-I	New course introduced as per NEP.
18.	21BPTAECC07(S)/ 21BPTAECC07(H)	Sanskrit/Hindi	New language courses introduced as per NEP.
19.	21BPTSEC05	Basic Life Support (BLS)	Theory and Practical course modules are merged and made as one course.
20.	21BPTSEC06	Basic skills in patient care-I	Converted from non-credit to credit course carrying 2 credits.
21.	21BPTSEC07	Professional ethics	Value based course introduced in 3rd semester instead of 7th semester as per NEP structure.
22.	21BPTDSC10	Exercise Therapy-II	Theory and Practical course modules are merged and made as one course.
23.	21BPTDSC11	Biomechanics and Kinesiology-II	Theory and Practical course modules are merged and made as one course.
24.	21BPTDSC12	Electro Physical Agents I and II	Earlier course name 'Electrotherapy' changed to Electro Physical Agents, and I and II which were in 3rd and 4th semesters separately have been merged into one course in 4th semester. This is to fulfill the curriculum structure of NEP.
25.	21BPTAECC08	French-II	New language course introduced as per NEP.
26.	21BPTAECC09(A)/ 21BPTAECC09(G)	Arabic/German	New language courses introduced as per NEP.
27.	21BPTAECC10	Constitution of India	Converted from non-credit to credit course carrying 2 credits.
28.	21BPTSEC08	Basic skills in patient care-II	Converted from non-credit to credit course carrying 2 credits.
29.	21BPTDSC13	General Medicine and Surgery	Separate courses earlier are now merged and made into one course.
30.	21BPTDSC14	OBG and Paediatrics	Separate courses earlier are now merged and made into one course.
31.	21BPTDSE01	Pharmacology	Earlier in 4th semester is now introduced as discipline specific elective course in 5 th semester.
32.	21BPTVOC01	Fitness Training	New vocational course introduced in 5 th semester as per NEP.
33.	21BPTSEC09	Mobilizations and Manipulations (peripheral and spinal joints)	New SEC course introduced as per NEP.
34.	21BPTSEC11	Yoga	Theory and Practical course modules are merged and made as one course.
35.	21BPTDSE02	Women's Health for Physiotherapists	Introduced as discipline specific elective course in 6 th semester.
36.	21BPTVOC02	Hospital Administration	Converted from non-credit to credit course carrying 3 credits.
37.	21BPTSEC13	NSS/Cultural/sports	Value based course added in 6 th semester as per NEP.
38.	21BPTDSE03	Electro diagnosis for Physiotherapists	Introduced as discipline specific elective course in 7 th semester.
39.	21BPTDSE04	Dry Needling	Introduced as discipline specific elective course in 7 th semester.
40.	21BPTVOC03	Essentials of Orthotics and Prosthetics	New vocational course introduced in 7 th semester as per NEP.

41.	21BPTDSE07	ICU monitoring and Management	Introduced as discipline specific elective course in 8 th semester.
42.	21BPTDSE08	Research Project	Introduced in 8 th semester as per NEP.
43.	21BPTVOC04	Medical coding	New vocational course introduced in 8 th semester as per NEP.

Total Number of Papers in BPT: 41
Total modifications done: 43
Percentage of Modifications: 60% (approx.)

3. To consider and approve the revised curriculum and syllabus for MPT 2021 batch.

- It was proposed by Dr. Rajasekar S and seconded by Dr. Thrishala Noronha that the curriculum and syllabus for MPT for the batch of 2021 be revised wherever necessary as per the latest trends in industry.

-Resolution: The members considered the curriculum and syllabus for BPT and discussed the necessary changes. Finally, it was approved and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval. It was also decided that the course can be introduced under College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University from 2021 batch onwards. The structuring and changes made are as follows:

Sl. No	Course Code	Course Name	Modification
1.	21MPT101	Research Methodology and Biostatistics for Physiotherapists	In module 3, handling SPSS added under processing and analysis of data. In module 5, writing references in research added under format of scientific documents.
2.	21MPT103	Evidence Based Practice in Physiotherapy	Both parts which were in one course, have been now separated into 2 courses to increase the credit value. Previous credits combined was 4, now revised as 4 and 2 respectively. Modules are redistributed.
3.	21MPT104	Ethics in Physiotherapy	
4.	21MPT105	Yoga Therapy	New course introduced for enhancing skills and application in physiotherapy carrying 2 credits.
5.	21MPT107	Clinical Training-I	Earlier the clinical training which was merged with other courses, is now separately put as a skill enhancement course for giving more consideration and credits to skill based training.
6.	21MPT202	Electrophysiology and Functional Diagnosis (Theory)	In module 1, 'Neurobiology of pain and pain modulations' withdrawn.
7.	21MPT206	Pain Science and Management	New course added with 2 credits.
8.	21MPT208	Clinical Training-II	New SEC added separately for skill based training.
9.	21MPT3G1	Physiotherapeutics-I (Theory)	Pain science and management topic withdrawn; credits revised from 2 to 4.
10.	21MPT3G2	Physiotherapeutics-I (Practical)	Pain assessment and management topic withdrawn.
11.	21MPT311	Advanced Assessment in Musculoskeletal and Sports Physiotherapy-I (Theory)	In module 1, history taking modified. Module 5 'Manual therapy concepts' replaced with 'Clinimetric properties of functional outcome measures.' New module 6 added.
12.	21MPT312	Advanced Musculoskeletal and Sports Goal Planning and Rehabilitation-I (Theory)	Under module 6, Physiotherapy management of locomotor disorders topic withdrawn and common

			drugs used in musculoskeletal conditions and their effect on orthopaedic rehabilitation added.
13.	21MPT313	Musculoskeletal and Sports Physiotherapy Assessment and Management-I (Practical)	In module 1, clinical reasoning in clinical practice added. Module 4, manual therapy concepts withdrawn.
14.	21MPT3G3	Entrepreneurship for Physiotherapists	New course added in 3rd semester carrying 2 credits.
15.	21MPT315-21MPT365	Clinical Training-III	New SEC added separately for skill based training across all electives.
16.	21MPT4G1	Physiotherapeutics-II (Theory)	Module 5 yogasanas and pranayama withdrawn.
17.	21MPT4G2	Physiotherapeutics-II (Practical)	Module 5 yogasanas and pranayama withdrawn.
18.	21MPT411	Advanced Assessment in Musculoskeletal and Sports Physiotherapy-II (Theory)	Module 1 manual therapy concepts modified; Kinesiotaping and sports taping withdrawn.
19.	21MPT412	Advanced Musculoskeletal and Sports Goal Planning and Rehabilitation-II (Theory)	Module 2 modified-wrist, elbow ankle added. Module 3 modified, new topics added and outdated topics withdrawn; Taping for acute and overuse injuries added.
20.	21MPT413	Musculoskeletal and Sports Physiotherapy Assessment and Management-II (Practical)	Module 1 manual therapy concepts modified. In module 2, Kinesiotaping and sports taping withdrawn. Module 5 and 6 modified.
21.	21MPT416	Kinetic control	Therapeutic taping replaced with kinetic control course.
22.	21MPT419/428/438/448/458/468	Clinical Training-IV	New SEC added separately for skill based training across all electives.
23.	21MPT351	Paediatric Sciences & Rehabilitation Assessment-I (Theory)	Module 2 added; module 3 and 4 modified.
24.	21MPT352	Paediatric Sciences & Rehabilitation Goal Planning and Management-I (Theory)	Module 1 newly added; module 2 modified; in module 6 Indian Public health initiatives added.
25.	21MPT451	Paediatric Sciences & Rehabilitation Assessment-II (Theory)	Module 1 newly added
26.	21MPT452	Paediatric Sciences & Rehabilitation Goal Planning and Management-II (Theory)	ICF model and SMART goals withdrawn; module 2 modified; module 5 and 6 added.
27.	21MPT453	Paediatric Rehabilitation Assessment & Management-II (Practical)	Module 5 and 6 added.
28.	21MPT361	Obstetrics and Gynaecology Physiotherapy Assessment I (Theory)	Module 1 and 5 modified; module 6 added.
29.	21MPT362	Obstetrics and Gynaecology Physiotherapy Goal Planning and Management-I (Theory)	Module 5 and 6 added.
30.	21MPT363	Obstetrics and Gynaecology Physiotherapy Assessment and	Module 5 modified; module 6 added.

		Management-I (Practical)	
31.	21MPT461	Obstetrics and Gynaecology Physiotherapy Assessment II (Theory)	Module 5, newborn assessment added.
32.	21MPT462	Obstetrics and Gynaecology Physiotherapy Goal Planning and Management-II (Theory)	Module 5 and 6 added.
33.	21MPT463	Obstetrics and Gynaecology Physiotherapy Assessment and Management-II (Practical)	Module 6 modified.

Total Number of Papers in MPT: 18
Total modifications done: 33
Percentage of Modifications: 40% (approx.)

4. Planning the academic calendar for BPT and MPT for the academic year 2021-22.

-Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar requested that the academic calendar for the odd semesters of BPT and MPT be planned for the year 2021-22 (November 2021- April 2022).

-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2021-22 of odd semesters of BPT and MPT, and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

5. Formation of Board of Examiners (BOE) for BPT and MPT program examination for 2021-22.

-The Chairperson explained the criteria related to the selection of BOE members and requested the Board to suggest names.

-Resolution: The Board prepared the list of BOE members in the Physiotherapy programmes for the academic year 2021-22 and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

6. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

-The Chairperson requested the Board members to prepare the panel of examiners for the odd semester end examination of BPT and MPT programs.

-Resolution: The Board members prepared the panel of examiners for the odd semester end examination of BPT and MPT, and resolved to recommend the same to the University and send the panel of examiners list in a sealed cover to Registrar (Evaluation).

The meeting started at 09.00 am and ended at 01.00 pm with Thanks to the Chair.

Dr. Rajasekar S
CHAIRPERSON (BOS)
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY